

Sustaining Real Estate Sector through Technological Interventions: Purchase Intention of Residential Apartment Buyers

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ABSTRACT

Technology is being widely adopted in Construction and Real Estate sector these days. Pandemic has made technology exigent in every walk of life and Real Estate sector is no exception to this paradigm. However, it must also be noted that technology is becoming a ubiquitous savior and an important tool for sustainability of enterprises. Real Estate has been a barometer for measuring progress of economy and its central theme of debate. If economy has to improve, much depends on revival of Real Estate Sector in general and retail purchase such as residential apartments in specific. Retail purchases have literally come to a halt due to various reasons such as frequent lock downs, non-movements, lack of confidence and absence of trust in future commitments. In this context, sustainability of this sector has been made possible by adoption of cutting edge technologies. In this paper the technologies are reviewed and how each brand is able to use technologies to better their marketing and sales efforts. The paper will also be able to convincingly illustrate technologies that could be used by companies that are smaller and medium scale in size, so that sustainability does not restrict itself to Tier I cities, but also revisits Tier II cities which are emerging markets.

Key Words: Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Big9, 360 Camera, Sustainability, Real Estate

INTRODUCTION

Real Estate is primarily an industry steeped in primitiveness and conventionality. To bring change to established practices is not going to be easy. The sector has been cautious thus far to adopt new and modern technologies due to various reasons both within and without (**Howard et al, 2007**). However, emergence of new technologies particularly Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality has gradually diffusing into Real Estate sector in an irrevocable manner. It shall be read in posterity that VR&AR technologies have completely and radically altered the ways how people conventionally thought and went about their property purchases (**Heinzel et al, 2017**). These technologies have been able to redraw strategies on how clients tend to see their design and able to visualize projects in a holistic manner. Besides they help to reach out and convince a potential client without the company needing to spend an additional pie. It shall be noted here that companies in developed nations have started to explore and examine power of mobile applications providing remote tours for potential buyers. (**Brenner,2017**). Among App developers, there is a huge requirement for apps relating to Real Estate say for instance Computer Vision Technology which is widely used in tracing, tracking and recognizing planar images besides objects like furniture items and others as though in real-time (**Sonje,2018**). It is worthwhile to note here that most of the studies have been focusing on distress in Real estate particularly during economic depression, but have hardly broached upon the concept of sustainability. In the present study we will be considering the question of sustainability of the industry covering the gap of sales and marketing efforts though adoption of technology. According to **Trulia (2017)** more than half of the home buyers and renters are likely to regret their decisions when there is lack of information or input asymmetry. Information regarding property, area coverage, facilities and others are often inadequate or concealed leading to customer dissatisfaction or mistrust. This is more pronounced in case of remote buyers who rely on property agents and other verbal commitments. Trust deficit arising out of such transactions are often detrimental to sustainability of business ventures.

Technologies come as a blessing to offset such trust deficits. Moreover, they also could reduce costs of advertising and marketing, which are significant cost centers in Real Estate and Property markets (**Wang et al, 2014**). Further the studies also indicate that technological interventions are found effective in enhancing the sale of residential apartments. These interventions need not be restricted for the last point of sale, but could also be effectively used from start of construction.

Further the studies also indicate that the technological interventions are found effective in enhancing the sale of residential apartments. These interventions need not be restricted for the last point of sale, but could also be effectively used from start of construction and process during construction. The latest imaging and video technologies can help buyers understand the building better and be more informed of key aspects related to electricity, plumbing alongside other critical elements that make up for quality. These inputs will help customers make rational property decisions, proper usage of area and land, reconstruction decisions for Vasthu compliance if any. The immersive user experience enabled by technology seems to establish a profound connection with customers and help them to assess construction quality, workmanship, space, aesthetics and other modifications well before they make up their minds on a purchase. The review of literature in this context will likely help in improving sustainability quotient among other sectors as well.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Digital technologies are making inroads in all walks of our life and its management. Adoption of these technologies assume no less significance in Real Estate Sector as well. Global innovation is beginning to have a bearing on this sector to make it more visible on the virtual world. Despite barriers and inhibitions when it comes to adoption of technology, Real estate sector has a lot of catching up to do in order to match their counterpart industries.

Smart Real Estate is powered by disruptive and innovative technologies that have come to known as Big9 (Ullah,2018). These Big9 technologies are key to transforming conventional Real Estate into Smart Real Estate (Allahmeh et al,2012). Use of these Big9 technologies centered around Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) can create a favorable environment for an ailing sector and make it more sustainable. The technologies and their description are given below in Figure 1

Figure 1: Technology and their area of operation

Sn	Technology	Description
1	Drone	It is an Unmanned aircraft, an autonomous flying object useful for accessing remote and difficult locations.

2	Internet of Things (IoT)	Internet of Things (IoT) is a paradigm of objects which are sensor based and seamlessly connected with one another and exchange data real time over the Internet.
3	Cloud Computing	It is a real time storage facility managed by cloud service providers. This is essentially a disaster recovery services providing back up to sensitive and confidential data.
4	Software as a Service (Saas)	A delivery and licensing model based technology. Usually an on demand software specifically created for niche industries and for sectors. Saas and Cloud computing together make up for a powerful combination of remote viewing and consumer history management for Business enterprises.
5	Big Data	A large quantum of data which are available in both structured and unstructured manner are analyzed using software to discover patterns useful to predict futuristic trends
6	3 D Scanning	Real time capturing and analysis of information, particularly of shapes and objects virtually to reconstruct digitally vibrant 3-D models for viewing in remote locations.
7	Wearable Technologies	Wearable are objects that are worn by humans for measured of data and technology based. They are usually smart electronic devices that are worn and data captured through them are stored on the cloud systems
8	Virtual and Augmented Reality	Virtual Reality has a gadget which provides an almost real time virtually generated experience to users. Gaming industry was the first to explore and adopt VR. Augmented Reality concerns with simulation of real time images with additional features to make assessment of commission or omission of certain aspects or features
9	AI and Robotics	Tasks are generally routine and may require lesser intelligence to handle. Thus these routine functions are automated and made intelligent using machine learning. They are flexible and improvise on learning capabilities.

Out of the Big 9 technologies that finds a prominent place in the use of smart Real Estate- Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR &AR) seems to be quite popular. The study by **Carter (2017)** reveals that over 90 % of stake holders wants to enhance their communication with tenants and buyers. The communication can be rendered totally effective with interventions of training. Virtual and Augmented Reality helps in training efforts related to safety, interaction, hands on and intuition.

Pousneh (2018) examined and explored the concept of perceptions amongst cross section of user customers. The study found that Augmented reality based experience helped in capturing and keeping customers' attention and improvising upon their perception. These perceptions in effect contribute towards positive choices and decision making. What exactly does an AR do? It is deployed to bring about a kaleidoscope blend of features integration of perception of customers through three dimensional comprehensive viewing.

The major challenge in adoption and utilization of these technologies lies in its development, ease of use and on their overall simplicity for early adoption. **Crowston et al (2001)** argues that there is an interplay between structure, information and underlying communications. This stands particularly true and relevant in Real Estate sector. For the consumers the information provided by realty agents is their measure towards purchase decisions. Moreover, what information does a prospect need? Anything that has to do with ease of collection, processing and holistic assimilation of information (**John Baen and Randall Guttery, 2020**).

There is a significant impact of ICT – Information, Communication and Technologies on commercial Real Estate in emerging and modern economies. The conceptual frameworks used are in absolute consonance with needs of the hour effectively mediated by technology (Tim Dixon,2005). Corporate Real Estate Managers are advised to take the help of technology in effectively intervening a property sale. Conventional concepts of time, space and place are giving way to the powerful and undeniable presence and utility of technology. This technology will become a core part of an overall business strategy (**Karen Gibler et al,2020**).

Figure 2: Studies on various aspects of Smart Real Estate

S N	Author(S)	Theme
1	Yuen et al (2011)	Virtual Reality allows users to walk through the site and construction process aiding in making relevant suggestions.
2	Musa (2018)	Intervention of technology aids and supports trust of consumers and contractors over a longer run.
3	Park et al (2013)	Construction defects and post purchase dissonance have been major factors of worry. This seems to be taken care by intervention of technology in the transaction.
4	Chong & Low (2005)	Proposed visualization techniques and mechanics to ensure the construction defects are taken care as and when it occurs. This they term as forward error correction mechanism.
5	Pantano & Servidio (2012)	Advocates utilization of visual technologies to address challenges of communication gap between customer and contractor. Moreover, simulations allow for a unique experience which make customers feel they are present. This according to the study advances a sense of trust between consumer and contractor.
6	Mahdjoubi et al (2013)	Argues that Real Estate sector is mostly using old, traditional and conventional techniques. This must be replaced with the assistance of technology when it comes to sale of property. Current challenges in adoption of these technologies include cost of installation and subsequent trainings.
7	Boga et al (2018)	Examines the effect of technology on the stake holders viz., agents, developers, buyers and other investors. Adoption of technology can largely reduce the overheads of travelling, reach out to maximum customers and reduce considerably advertising and marketing costs.

8	Ullah et al (2017)	There is a key concern among buyers of property, specifically residential apartments. And this willingness is measured through the intention. Past studies have linked a purchase of property to the ability of client to identify with the property. And technology can enhance the identification of consumer with property.
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Conceptual Model

Figure 3 : Conceptual Model

Customer Intentions are measured and modeled on stake holders' attributes and expectations. Further, Quality information, service and system are essential to sustain brand image. In our model, we have integrated the model of Technology acceptance and set antecedents to the same with stake holders and SIS Quality.

SCOPE AND FURTHER STUDY

The conceptual model is based on rough and abstract collection of literature. It is advised that a proper and critical review of literature shall help in bringing about a certain quantum of stability on the model. Further, this model is conceptual in nature and must pass the test of

empiricist. Collection of data and analyzing through appropriate software will lead to confirmation of model.

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